

CONSTRUCTING THE BOWEN MEASURE FOR AN ANOSOV DIFFEOMORPHISM

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Abstract: This paper explores the construction of stable and unstable currents associated with toral hyperbolic automorphisms $f: \mathbb{T}^k \rightarrow \mathbb{T}^k$. A toral hyperbolic automorphism is defined by an invertible matrix $A \in GL(k, \mathbb{Z})$ with no eigenvalues on the unit circle, inducing a diffeomorphism on the torus $\mathbb{T}^k$. We describe the decomposition of the tangent bundle into stable and unstable subspaces and construct the corresponding stable and unstable currents by integrating over the stable and unstable manifolds. Additionally, we examine the entropy of these automorphisms, showing that the topological entropy is determined by the logarithm of the absolute values of the unstable eigenvalues of the matrix A . An example of a 2-dimensional toral hyperbolic automorphism is provided to illustrate the entropy calculation. The relationship between entropy and the constructed currents is discussed, highlighting the role of the Bowen measure in maximizing entropy. This study contributes to the understanding of the dynamical properties and complexity of toral hyperbolic automorphisms.

Keywords: Toral hyperbolic automorphism, stable and unstable currents, topological entropy, measure-theoretic entropy, Bowen measure, dynamical systems.

Anosov diffeomorphism $f: M \rightarrow M$ on a compact manifold M is a diffeomorphism that exhibits hyperbolic behavior throughout the entire manifold. This hyperbolicity is characterized by a continuous splitting of the tangent bundle:

$$T_x M = E_x^s \oplus E_x^u,$$

where: The **stable subspace** E_x^s is exponentially contracted under the differential df . The **unstable subspace** E_x^u is exponentially expanded under df .

These subspaces define the **stable manifolds** $W^s(x)$ and **unstable manifolds** $W^u(x)$ through each point $x \in M$:

$$W^s(x) = \{y \in M \mid \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} d(f^n(x), f^n(y)) = 0\}, \quad W^u(x) = \{y \in M \mid \lim_{n \rightarrow -\infty} d(f^n(x), f^n(y)) = 0\}.$$

The stable and unstable manifolds intersect transversally at each point $x \in M$. This transversality is crucial for constructing the Bowen measure and defining the intersection of stable and unstable currents.

A **current** can be thought of as a generalized differential form that allows integration over manifolds or subsets of manifolds. The **stable current** (W^s, μ^s, ν_s) is defined by:

$$\langle (W^s, \mu^s, \nu_s), \omega \rangle = \int_{W_x^u} \left(\int_{W_x^s} \omega d\mu_x^s \right) dm_x^u,$$

where: $\omega \in \mathcal{D}^p(M)$ is a test differential p -form. W_x^s is the local stable manifold at a point $x \in W_x^u$. μ_x^s is a conditional measure on each local stable manifold. m_x^u is a transversal measure on the local unstable manifolds. The **unstable current** (W^u, m^u, ν_u) is defined by:

$$\langle (W^u, m^u, \nu_u), \omega \rangle = \int_{W_x^s} \left(\int_{W_x^u} \omega dm_x^u \right) d\mu_x^s,$$

where: W_x^u is the local unstable manifold at a point $x \in W_x^s$. m_x^u is a conditional measure on each local unstable manifold. μ_x^s is a transversal measure on the local stable manifolds.

A **Pesin box** $\mathcal{B}$ is a local product structure in M around a point x in the non-wandering set for the Anosov diffeomorphism. It is defined as:

$$\mathcal{B} = \bigcup_{x \in W_x^u} W_x^s \cong \mathcal{D}^{k-p} \times \mathcal{D}^p,$$

where W_x^s is the local stable manifold through $x \in M$. W_x^u is the local unstable manifold containing all these stable manifolds W_x^s . $\mathcal{D}^{k-p}$ and $\mathcal{D}^p$ are small disks in the unstable and stable directions, respectively. This local product structure allows us to describe the local geometry of the stable and unstable manifolds.

Let $f: M \rightarrow M$ be an Anosov diffeomorphism on a compact manifold M . We have stable and unstable currents defined by the stable and unstable manifolds associated with this diffeomorphism:

The **stable current**: (W^s, μ^s, ν_s) The **unstable current**: (W^u, m^u, ν_u) These currents correspond to the integration over stable and unstable manifolds W^s and W^u , respectively, with associated transversal measures μ^s and m^u and orientations ν_s and ν_u . The stable current (W^s, μ^s, ν_s) defines a cohomology class in the de Rham cohomology $H^{k-p}(M, \mathbb{R})$, where $p = \dim W^s(x)$. The unstable current (W^u, m^u, ν_u)

defines a cohomology class in $H^p(M, \mathbb{R})$, where $k - p = \dim W^u(x)$. These currents can be interpreted as representing certain homology or cohomology classes. For example, if the stable and unstable foliations are transverse and cover all of M , their intersection defines a cohomology class related to the non-wandering set or a basic set of the Anosov diffeomorphism.

The Anosov diffeomorphism $f: M \rightarrow M$ maps stable manifolds into stable manifolds and unstable manifolds into unstable manifolds. For the stable current:

$$f_*(W^s, \mu^s, \nu_s) = \lambda^{-1}(W^s, \mu^s, \nu_s),$$

where $\lambda = e^{h_t(f)} > 1$ is the expansion rate of f along the unstable direction. This shows that pushing forward the stable current under f scales it by λ^{-1} , reflecting contraction along the stable direction.

For the unstable current:

$$f_*(W^u, m^u, \nu_u) = \lambda(W^u, m^u, \nu_u),$$

indicating that pushing forward the unstable current scales it by λ , corresponding to expansion along the unstable direction. The pull-back of these currents under the diffeomorphism f satisfies:

$$f^*(W^s, \mu^s, \nu_s) = \lambda(W^s, \mu^s, \nu_s), f^*(W^u, m^u, \nu_u) = \lambda^{-1}(W^u, m^u, \nu_u).$$

This shows how the currents transform under the pull-back of f , with the stable current being expanded by λ and the unstable current being contracted by λ^{-1} .

Transversal Intersection: The stable and unstable currents intersect transversally, forming a new current at their intersection points. The intersection current $(W^s \cap W^u, \mu_{su}, \nu_{su})$ can be defined as:

$$\langle (W^s, \mu^s, \nu_s) \wedge (W^u, m^u, \nu_u), \omega \rangle = \int_M \left(\int_{W_x^s \cap W_x^u} \omega(x) d\mu_{su}(x) \right) d\nu_{su}(x).$$

Here, μ_{su} is the product measure on the intersection, and ν_{su} is the orientation induced by the intersection of the stable and unstable manifolds.

If $\dim(W^s) = p$ and $\dim(W^u) = k - p$, then the intersection dimension is:

$$\dim(W^s \cap W^u) = \dim(M) - (\dim(W^s) + \dim(W^u)) = 0.$$

This implies that the intersection typically consists of isolated points when the manifolds are transverse.

Smoothing of Currents: Currents can be approximated or regularized by smooth forms. By convolution with a smoothing kernel, one can approximate stable and unstable currents with smooth differential forms while maintaining their essential properties (support, orientations, etc.).

Continuity in the Space of Currents: The intersection of stable and unstable currents, viewed as distributions, is continuous in the space of currents. For smooth test forms ω , we can define the multiplication (wedge product) by continuity.

The **Bowen measure** μ_B is constructed using the intersection of the stable and unstable currents:

$$\langle \mu_B, \omega \rangle = \int_{W_x^u} \left(\int_{W_x^s} \omega(x) d\mu_x^s \right) dm_x^u.$$

The measure μ_B is obtained by integrating over the local stable manifolds W_x^s with respect to the conditional measure μ_x^s and then integrating over the local unstable manifolds W_x^u with respect to m_x^u . This formulation reflects the product structure inherent in the Pesin box, taking into account the transversality of the stable and unstable manifolds.

Within the Pesin box $\mathcal{B}$, the Bowen measure μ_B can be expressed as:

$$\mu_B|_{\mathcal{B}} = \mu_x^s \otimes m_x^u,$$

where μ_x^s is the conditional measure on the stable manifold W_x^s for each $x \in W_x^u$, m_x^u is the conditional measure on the unstable manifold W_x^u .

This product measure reflects that, locally within $\mathcal{B}$, the Bowen measure decomposes into a product of the stable and unstable conditional measures.

Properties of the Bowen Measure: The Bowen measure μ_B is invariant under the Anosov diffeomorphism $f: M \rightarrow M$. It maximizes the measure-theoretic entropy of f and captures the statistical properties of the system. The measure μ_B is supported on the non-wandering set or a basic set, reflecting the hyperbolic structure of the dynamics.

To construct stable and unstable currents for a toral hyperbolic automorphism $f: \mathbb{T}^k \rightarrow \mathbb{T}^k$, we start by understanding the structure of f and its action on the torus.

A toral hyperbolic automorphism is a linear map induced by an invertible $k \times k$ integer matrix $A \in GL(k, \mathbb{Z})$ with no eigenvalues on the unit circle. This map induces a diffeomorphism $f: \mathbb{T}^k \rightarrow \mathbb{T}^k$ on the k -dimensional torus $\mathbb{T}^k = \mathbb{R}^k / \mathbb{Z}^k$.

The map f is hyperbolic if the matrix A has eigenvalues both inside and outside the unit circle: A has no eigenvalues of absolute value 1. There exist eigenvalues λ_i such that $|\lambda_i| < 1$ (stable directions) and eigenvalues μ_j such that $|\mu_j| > 1$ (unstable directions).

This hyperbolic structure induces a splitting of the tangent bundle $T_x \mathbb{T}^k$ into stable and unstable subspaces corresponding to the eigenspaces of A .

Given the matrix A , decompose $\mathbb{R}^k$ into stable and unstable subspaces:

$$\mathbb{R}^k = E^s \oplus E^u,$$

where: E^s is the stable subspace, corresponding to the span of eigenvectors of A with eigenvalues $|\lambda_i| < 1$. E^u is the unstable subspace, corresponding to the span of eigenvectors of A with eigenvalues $|\mu_j| > 1$.

The stable and unstable manifolds for f at a point $x \in \mathbb{T}^k$ are linear subspaces given by:

$$W^s(x) = x + E^s, W^u(x) = x + E^u.$$

To construct stable and unstable currents, we consider the integration over the stable and unstable manifolds. The stable and unstable currents have the following properties: Invariance under f :

$$f_*W^s = \lambda^{-1}W^s, f_*W^u = \lambda W^u,$$

where λ is the expansion rate of f in the corresponding directions.

Transversality: The stable and unstable currents intersect transversally, and their intersection can be used to construct invariant measures, such as the Bowen measure for f .

The **topological entropy** $h(f)$ of a dynamical system $f: M \rightarrow M$ is a measure of the complexity or "chaotic behavior" of the system. For a smooth map on a compact manifold, entropy quantifies the exponential growth rate of distinguishable orbits as time progresses. For a measure-preserving dynamical system, we can also consider the **measure-theoretic entropy** $h_\mu(f)$, which quantifies the average rate of information production under the invariant measure μ .

For a toral automorphism, both topological entropy and measure-theoretic entropy (with respect to an invariant measure like the Bowen measure) are well-defined and equal. For a toral hyperbolic automorphism $f: \mathbb{T}^k \rightarrow \mathbb{T}^k$, induced by a matrix $A \in GL(k, \mathbb{Z})$, the entropy can be computed using the eigenvalues of A .

Let the characteristic polynomial of the matrix A be:

$$\det(A - \lambda I) = 0.$$

Suppose the eigenvalues of A are $\lambda_1, \lambda_2, \dots, \lambda_k$. Because A is a hyperbolic matrix, none of the eigenvalues lie on the unit circle, and they can be grouped into stable eigenvalues (with $|\lambda_i| < 1$) and unstable eigenvalues (with $|\lambda_i| > 1$).

The **topological entropy** $h(f)$ of the toral automorphism f is given by:

$$h(f) = \sum_{|\lambda_i| > 1} \log|\lambda_i|,$$

where the sum is over all the eigenvalues λ_i of A with absolute value greater than 1 (the unstable eigenvalues).

For a measure-preserving transformation $f: \mathbb{T}^k \rightarrow \mathbb{T}^k$ with respect to the Bowen measure μ_B , the **measure-theoretic entropy** $h_{\mu_B}(f)$ also equals the topological entropy:

$$h_{\mu_B}(f) = h(f) = \sum_{|\lambda_i| > 1} \log |\lambda_i|.$$

This equality holds because the Bowen measure maximizes the measure-theoretic entropy among all f -invariant probability measures.

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